

A new monotypic acronictine noctuid moth genus from East Africa (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Acronictinae)

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Abstract – *Corniculonycta* Kiss & Clifton, gen. nov. and *Corniculonycta politzari* Kiss & Clifton, sp. nov. are described, based on 48 specimens from East Africa (Kenya: Kakamega Forest, Uganda: Kalinzu Forest, Kibale Forest). The only known species of the genus lives in the remnants of the lowland rain forest. A proper diagnosis and descriptions are given for the genus and the species, the characteristics of the last abdominal segments are emphasized. With 32 figures.

Key words – Kakamega Forest, Kalinzu Forest, Kenya, Kibale Forest, lowland rain forest, *Megalonycta*, Uganda

INTRODUCTION

During the review of the Acronictinae material of several institutional and private collections with special reference to type specimens, material of a previously unknown African species under the name “*Acronicta kakamega* Clifton” was found in the private collection of the late Gottfried Behounek (Grafing bei München, Germany) by the first author. Soon, additional specimens were found in the Zoologische Staatssammlung München (Germany) from the Politzar collection; and most recently in the Museum für Naturkunde (Berlin, Germany) and Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart (Germany). Checking the relevant literature (e.g. GAEDE 1934–1940, JANSE 1937–1939) and the online database AfroMoths (DE PRINS & DE PRINS 2021) it turned out that “*Acronicta kakamega*” is a manuscript name as it has not been published.

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The proper diagnosis of Acronictinae is still missing since it is often limited to regional faunas or inaccurate as a result of including non-acronictine genera (SCHMIDT & ANWEILER 2020). On the other hand, SCHMIDT & ANWEILER (2020) have selected some additional genera and prepared a general diagnosis for the subfamily, emphasized the unusually high morphological variation in adults but pointed to the anterolateral sclerites of the 8th segment to be the most consistent morphological character.

The external and genitalia characters of "*Acronicta kakamega*" are closer to those of the African acronictine genus *Megalonycta* Viette, 1965 than any *Acronicta* species (e.g. KONONENKO 2010, SCHMIDT & ANWEILER 2020). Furthermore, comparing characters provided by male and female genitalia and the structure of the last abdominal segments, the result suggests that "*Acronicta kakamega*" is not only an undescribed species but representative of a hitherto unrecognized distinct genus.

The aim of this paper is to characterize this interesting taxon via giving a proper diagnosis and description compatible for the future works planned to run on the subfamily.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Adult habitus pictures were photographed with Canon Eos 550D with Tamron AF 90 mm F2.8 Di Macro 1:1 SP objective and Samsung Galaxy A11 smartphone. Genitalia were dissected using 15% potassium hydroxide (KOH) to macerate the full abdomen. Cleaned abdominal segments, genital capsule, everted vesica and female copulatory organ were dehydrated in 96% ethanol with Eosin dye to stain the weakly sclerotized structures for a night then mounting to Euparal. Genitalia of the holotype were mounted to Canada balsam. Genitalia slides were photographed with Olympus DP70 digital microscope camera connected with an Olympus SZX12 zoom stereo microscope and Wild Heerbrugg WILD M5A stereo microscope. Digital images were adjusted with the program Adobe Photoshop CS6.

Terminology for morphological characters follows KISS (2017) and supplemented by SCHMIDT & ANWEILER (2020) where necessary. Material examined belongs to the following private and institutional collections: GB = collection of the late Gottfried Behounek, deposited in ZSM; MfN = Museum für Naturkunde (Berlin, Germany); MHNG = Muséum d'histoire naturelle (Geneva, Switzerland); NMK = National Museums of Kenya (Nairobi, Kenya); SMNS = Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart (Germany); ZISP = Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint-Petersburg, Russia); ZMUC = Zoological Museum, University of Copenhagen (Denmark); ZSM = Zoologische Staatssammlung München (Germany).

developed clavus covered with some sparse, soft hairs; the smaller, moderately sclerotized sacculus covered by somewhat softer, finer long hairs; the long, moderately sclerotized medial sclerite; the moderately sclerotized, rounded, wedge-shaped unilateral carina-like extension on the phallus; the more simpler, shorter and wider vesica with a long, strongly ribbed, rugulose crest and a moderately large, sclerotized, spur-like diverticulum.

The female genitalia of *Corniculonycta* (Figs 17–18) are resembled to e.g. *Craniophora ligustri* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (see KISS 2017: 20, Figs 33–34), however, the similarity is only superficial and not indicating closer relationship (such as in between *Megalonycta* and *Berionycta* Kiss, 2017; see KISS 2017). Comparing to *Megalonycta* (Figs 19–21), *Corniculonycta* has remarkably larger female copulatory organ; a more ribbed, sclerotized and proximally wider ductus bursae connecting to appendix-corporis bursae laterally; a more sophisticated appendix of the fused corpus bursae and appendix bursae complex with two, moderately large, slightly sclerotized patches.

The male 7th and 8th abdominal segments (Figs 22–23), comparing to those of *Megalonycta* (Figs 24–27), have a distally more narrower 7th sternite with wider distal sclerotized part; a much wider, quadrangular 7th tergite with indistinct, shallow, rather V-shaped window; a more sclerotized, distally conspicuously wider 8th sternite proximally strongly extending to the 7th segment, and with a larger intersegmental membrane without the posterior abdominal brush and with smaller, more or less triangular or roof tile-shaped window; a chiasma-shaped 8th tergite with rhomboidal window; a shorter, straighter anterolateral sclerites of the 8th segment conspicuously fused with the proximal edge of 8th sternite forming a narrow, sclerotized margin.

The female 7th abdominal segment (Figs 28–29) can be distinguished from that of *Megalonycta* (Figs 30–32) by the shorter tergite; and the shorter, somewhat wider sternite with large, semi-circular window along the distal edge.

Etymology – The name of the new genus refers to the horn-shaped ventral extension of valvae (“*corniculum*”) and the membership of Acronictinae (“*Acronycta*”).

Figures 1–10. Adults of *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov., *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* and *M. inversa*: 1 = *C. politzari*, HT, male, Kenya, Kakamega, NMK-INV-T-672, slide No. MC 3-2022 (coll. NMK); 2 = *C. politzari*, PT, male, Kenya, Kakamega, slide No. KA1431m (coll. ZSM); 3 = *C. politzari*, PT, male, Kenya, Kakamega, slide No. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 4 = *C. politzari*, PT, male, Uganda, Kibale N. P., slide No. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 5 = *C. politzari*, PT, female, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 6 = *C. politzari*, PT, female, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 7 = *M. forsteri*, male, Ethiopia, slide No. KA894m (coll. ZMUC); 8 = *M. forsteri*, female, Ethiopia, slide No. KA2191f (coll. GB); 9 = *M. paragrapha*, male, Republic of South Africa, slide No. KA2121m (coll. SMNS); 10 = *M. inversa*, female, Rwanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, slide No. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Scale bar = 10 mm. (Photos by L. Njoroge: Fig. 1; Á. Kiss: Figs 2–10).

Figures 11–16. Male genitalia (valvae and aedeagus with everted vesica) of *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov., *Megalonycta forsteri* and *M. inversa*: 11 = *C. politzari*, HT, Kenya, Kakamega, NMK-INV-T-672, slide No. MC 3-2022 (coll. NMK) (unscaled, uneverted vesica); 12 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, slide No. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 13 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, slide No. KA1432m (coll. ZSM); 14 = *C. politzari*, PT, Uganda, Kibale N. P., slide No. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 15 = *M. forsteri*, Ethiopia, slide No. KA895m (coll. ZMUC); 16 = *M. inversa*, HT, Tanzania, slide No. KA1471m (coll. MfN). Scale bar = 1 mm. (Photos by L. Njoroge: Fig. 11; Á. Kiss: Figs 12–16). The background of the valval androconial tufts is darker due to the limitations of graphical possibilities.

Figures 17–21. Female genitalia of *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov., *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* and *M. inversa*: 17 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 18 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 19 = *M. forsteri*, Ethiopia, slide No. KA2191f (coll. GB); 20 = *M. paragrapha*, Republic of South Africa, slide No. KA1470f (coll. MfN); 21 = *M. inversa*, Rwanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, slide No. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Scale bar = 1 mm. (Photos by Á. Kiss).

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Figures 22–27. Male 7th and 8th abdominal segments of *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov., *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* and *M. inversa*: 22 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, slide No. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 23 = *C. politzari*, PT, Uganda, Kibale N. P., slide No. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 24 = *M. forsteri*, Ethiopia, slide No. KA895m (coll. ZMUC); 25 = *M. forsteri*, Ethiopia, slide No. KA1417m (coll. GB); 26 = *M. paragrapha*, Republic of South Africa, slide No. KA2126m (coll. SMNS); 27 = *M. inversa*, HT, Tanzania, slide No. KA1471m (coll. MfN). Left side sternite, right side tergite. Scale bar = 1 mm. (Photos by Á. Kiss).

Figures 28–32. Female 7th abdominal segment of *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov., *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* and *M. inversa*: 28 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 29 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., slide No. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 30 = *M. forsteri*, Ethiopia, slide No. KA2191f (coll. GB); 31 = *M. paragrapha*, Republic of South Africa, slide No. KA1470f (coll. MfN); 32 = *M. inversa*, Rwanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, slide No. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Left side tergite, right side sternite. Scale bar = 1 mm. (Photos by Á. Kiss).

***Corniculonycta politzari* Kiss & Clifton, sp. nov.**

(Figs 1–6, 11–14, 17–18, 22–23, 28–29)

Type material – Holotype, male, Kenya, Kakamega Forest, January 1973, leg. Dr. H. Politzar, NMK-INV-T-672, slide No.: MC 3-2022 (coll. NMK) (Figs 1, 11). Paratypes (n = 47). KENYA. 4 males, 2 females, with same data as the holotype, NMK-INV-T 666 (abdomen missing) – NMK-INV-T 668, NMK-INV-T 671, NMK-INV-T 684, NMK-INV-T 685 (abdomen missing); 6 males, 5 females, with same locality as the holotype, June 1957, leg. C.R. Howard, NMK-INV-T 689 (coll. NMK); October–November 1969, leg. B. Watulege, NMK-INV-T 679 (coll. NMK); 22.IV.1973, leg. Dr. H. Politzar, NMK-INV-T 673, NMK-INV-T 675, NMK-INV-T 686 (coll. NMK); 19.VIII.1973, leg. Dr. H. Politzar, NMK-INV-T

669, NMK-INV-T 670, NMK-INV-T 674, NMK-INV-T 676, NMK-INV-T 687, NMK-INV-T 688 (coll. NMK); 13 males, 5 females, Kakamega, September 1961, leg. N. Milton, NMK-INV-T 681 (coll. NMK); November 1964, leg. E. Carcasson, NMK-INV-T 658, NMK-INV-T 660 (genitalia on card on pin) – NMK-INV-T 662 (coll. NMK); March 1966, leg. R.H. Carcasson, NMK-INV-T 659, NMK-INV-T 663 – NMK-INV-T 665 (slide Nos: 515–518, slides of both wings, fore, mid and hind legs and genitalia), NMK-INV-T 678, NMK-INV-T 680, NMK-INV-T 683 (coll. NMK); December 1966, leg. R.H. Carcasson & A. Forbes-Watson, NMK-INV-T 677, NMK-INV-T 682 (coll. NMK); 03.I.1973, leg. H. Politzar, slide No.: KA1431m (coll. ZSM) (Fig. 2); 23.IV.1973, leg. H. Politzar, slide Nos: KA979m (Figs 3, 12, 22), KA980m, KA1432m (Fig. 13) (coll. ZSM); 1 female, 1 specimen [sex not possible to identify], Western Kakamega Forest N. R., Buyangu Hill (view point), 1667 m, 0°20'45.93"N, 34°51'54.58"E, 18.I.2004, at light, 18.30–23.30 h, leg. F. Haas, J. Holstein & A. Zahm, slide No.: KA2113f (coll. SMNS) (Figs 5, 17, 28), 30.I.2004, at light, 19.00–22.00 h, leg. J. Holstein & A. Zahm (coll. SMNS); 3 specimens [sex not possible to identify], Western Kakamega Forest N. R., vic. Buyangu, Buyangu Hill (view point), 1700 m, 0°20'45.93"N, 34°51'54.58"E, 22.XI.2002, at light, leg. D. Bartsch & A. Zahm (coll. SMNS), 0°20'45.93"N, 34°51'54.58"E, primary forest, 27.IX.2005, at light, 19–23 h, leg. D. Bartsch & J. Holstein (coll. SMNS); 1 female, 3 specimens [sex not possible to identify], Western Kakamega Forest N. R., vic. Buyangu, Southern Buyangu Hill, 1600 m, 27.I.2004, at light, 19.30–22.00 h, leg. J. Holstein & A. Zahm, slide No.: KA2114f (coll. SMNS) (Figs 6, 18, 29). UGANDA. 1 male, Kalinzu Forest, Ankole, November 1961, leg. R.H. Carcasson, NMK-INV-T 690, slide No.: MC 4-2022 (coll. NMK); 1 male, Kibale National Park, Biol. Field Station, 19–24. XI.2014, at light, leg. W. Mey, slide No.: KA1870m (coll. MfN) (Figs 4, 14, 23); 1 male, Kibale Biol. Field Station of Maker SU, 1511 m, 00°33'68"N, 30°21'42"E, 19–24.X.2014, at light, leg. V. V. Anikin, slide No.: Matov0405m (coll. ZISP).

Diagnosis – *Corniculonycta politzari* (Figs 1–6) externally resembles to certain variant of the species of *Megalonycta*, e.g. *M. forsteri* Laporte, 1979 (Figs 7–8), *M. paragrapha* (Felder, 1868) (Fig. 9) and *M. inversa* (Gaede, 1915) (Fig. 10), however, it differs by the much narrower, apically slightly more elongated forewing; the much shorter basal streak with smaller and shorter, more or less indistinct suprabasal patch; the generally more conspicuous whitish patch in the medial field at the inner margin of the forewing; the more reduced tornal streak without the fishbone-like pattern; the conspicuous dark spots between the orbicular and reniform stigmata, at the base and the end of the tornal streak; the more indistinct antemedial line; the more reduced, indistinct orbicular and reniform stigmata; the less prominent, rather line-like apical dash and tornal patch; the extra, indistinct, dark patch-like band at the inner base of hindwing.

Diagnostic characters for genitalia and abdominal segments are given in the diagnostic and descriptive entries of the genus (see above).

Description – Imago (Figs 1–6): Wingspan 31–35 mm in males, 35–37 mm in females. No sexual dimorphism. Head large, greyish-white; 2nd segment of palpus longer than 3rd segment and equal in length in both sexes; antennae in both sexes filiform, basal part covered with whitish scales. Thorax wide, greyish-white scattered with blackish scales; patagia of same colour as thorax with wider blackish outline; tegulae of same colour as thorax with blackish spot at inner base next to patagia and blackish tip; metathorax with irregular shaped blackish spots. Forewing long, evenly narrow, apically slightly elongated, tornally slightly angled or rounded; greyish-white scattered with light and dark brownish scales and with pale purplish shading; basal streak blackish, short, wedge-shaped, reduced or often absent; tornal streak blackish, thin, reduced or absent and substituted by dark patches between medial and subterminal lines; tornal patch blackish, narrow, long, line-like next to vein Cu_2 ; apical dash blackish, very thin, line-like or absent; suprabasal patch greyish-white with or without whitish quadrangular or spot-like patch next to basal streak; subbasal patch whitish, bordered with some light brownish scales; subbasal line blackish, double, strongly reduced; basal field greyish-white or brownish; antemedial line blackish, double, wavy, strongly reduced, filled with some whitish scales; inner part of medial field relatively wide, lighter greyish-white with brown, at inner margin with often conspicuous whitish patch; medial line blackish, thin, zigzagged; medial fascia two blackish-brown patches; outer part of medial field narrow, lighter greyish-white; postmedial line double, crenulated, with whitish cap-like patches between veins M_3-Cu_1 and Cu_1-Cu_2 and more conspicuous at inner margin; subterminal field greyish-white with two dark patches at veins M_2 and Cu_2, A_{1+2} ; subterminal line blackish, formed by strongly reduced, hastate spots; terminal field greyish with more whitish spots; terminal line whitish, interrupted with narrow, blackish lines at veins; claviform stigma absent; orbicular stigma strongly reduced, blackish outlined, filled with greyish-white scales; reniform stigma strongly reduced, blackish outlined at inner margin and with three blackish dots at outer margin; fringe blackish, chequered with whitish pattern. Hindwing rounded, slightly triangular, greyish-brown; marginal band absent; tornal patch reduced, with some blackish scales at vein Cu_2 ; discal line strongly reduced, with only some dark, indistinct patches at veins M_2, Cu_2 and A_1 ; discal spot faint or absent; indistinct, dark patch-like band presented at inner base of hindwing; fringe greyish-brown, chequered with whitish. Abdomen greyish-white with scattered brownish scales; middorsal scale tuft greyish-white with blackish tip between 2nd and 4th segments, on 2nd segment larger; in females, blackish scales laterally on the intersegmental membrane of 7th segments.

Male genitalia (Figs 11–14): Uncus cylindrical, moderately short, curved, basally wider, apically narrowing, ended in relatively long, thin hook, basally and medially sparsely hairy; scaphium weakly sclerotized, membranous; subscaphium absent; tegumen moderately sclerotized, evenly wide, longer than vinculum; peniculus short, slightly protruding, basally conspicuously tapering

with slightly more sclerotized edge; vinculum wide, curved; saccus U-shaped, rounded, moderately sclerotized; juxta more or less weakly sclerotized, rounded, joining with slightly more sclerotized, larger, button-like part distally; transtilla moderately sclerotized, relatively short; valvae moderately sclerotized, evenly moderately narrow, wavy with long, horn-shaped ventral extension in apical third; costa basally less, apically somewhat more sclerotized, strongly wavy; cucullus rounded, reduced; corona absent; clavus moderately developed, covered with some sparse, soft hairs; sacculus less developed, moderately sclerotized, covered with soft, finer long hairs; medial sclerite moderately sclerotized, more or less straight. Phallus tubular, relatively long and narrow, at coecum somewhat widened; carina moderately sclerotized, rounded, wedge-shaped unilateral extension. Vesica tubular, simple, weakly sclerotized with membranous basal diverticulum, long, strongly ribbed, rugulose crest and moderately large, sclerotized, spur-like diverticulum distally.

Female genitalia (Figs 17–18): Ovipositor rounded, weakly sclerotized; papillae anales weakly sclerotized, elongated, densely hairy; anterior and posterior apophysis moderately sclerotized, rod-like, equal in length; anterior apophysis proximally with bulb-like extension then tapering; antrum more or less oval, weakly sclerotized, junction with ductus bursae narrow, weakly sclerotized, slightly ribbed; ductus bursae moderately long, distally much narrower than proximally, evenly moderately sclerotized, strongly ribbed, junction with appendix-corporis bursae complex widened; corpus bursae and appendix bursae fused into weakly sclerotized, sack-like complex with large unilateral, sclerotized patch; appendix bursae half in size compared to corpus bursae with moderately ribbed, rounded end.

Male 7th and 8th abdominal segments (Figs 22–23): 7th sternite slightly trapezoidal, longer than wide, distal part slightly more sclerotized; proximal edge straight; lateral sides strongly convex; basal edge slightly concave, indented in middle. 7th tergite more or less trapezoidal, longer than wide, with slightly more sclerotized, semi-circular distal band and shallow, narrow U- or V-shaped window; proximal edge straight with two curved, slightly stronger sclerotized rods; lateral sides finely concave with rounded corner; distal edge slightly concave or more or less straight. 8th sternite strongly sclerotized, trapezoidal, proximally narrower than distally and extending in the 7th–8th intersegmental membrane; proximal edge wavy, moderately sclerotized, connected to strongly sclerotized, more or less straight, rod-like anterolateral sclerites of 8th segment with continuous, sclerotized edge through proximal half of lateral sides; lateral sides wavy, rather widely sclerotized with distally spur-like lateral extension and in middle, not reaching distal edge; distal edge widely membranous, straight or slightly concave, indented in middle; window more or less triangular or roof tile-shaped; posterior abdominal brush absent. 8th tergite chiasma-shaped, moderately sclerotized; proximal edge curved, apically rounded with membranous, shallow

pocket-like lateral extension; lateral sides curved, proximally widely fused, distally triangular; distal edge straight; window more or less rhomboidal.

Female 7th abdominal segments (Figs 28–29): 7th sternite quadrangular, wider than long, slightly sclerotized with slightly more sclerotized, semi-circular distal band, and distally narrow, slightly sclerotized window; proximal edge more or less straight; lateral sides somewhat wavy or straight; distal edge membranous, concave. 7th tergite quadrangular, longer than wide, slightly sclerotized with slightly more sclerotized band in the distal third quarters with distally extending U-like window; proximal edge more or less straight with two curved, slightly stronger sclerotized rods; lateral sides more or less straight; distal edge straight or slightly curved.

Etymology – The new species is dedicated to the late Dr Karlheinz Politzar (1938–2007), a great tropical veterinary surgeon and collector of African Lepidoptera.

Distribution and bionomy – The new species is currently known only from a few, strongly isolated lowland rain forests, such as the “Lake Victoria drier peripheral semi-evergreen Guineo-Congolian rain forest” (Kenya: Kakamega Forest) and the “Lake Victoria transitional rain forest” (Uganda: Kalinzu Forest, Kibale Forest) (VAN BREUGEL et al. 2015). However, it is highly possible that the species can be found in the remnant of these rain forests around Lake Victoria.

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Új monotipikus bagolyepke génusz Kelet-Afrikából (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Acronictinae)

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Összefoglalás – A *Corniculonycta* gen. nov. és a *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. 48 példány alapján kerül leírásra, melyeket Kelet-Afrikában (Kenya: Kakamega Erdő, Uganda: Kalinzu Erdő, Kibale Erdő) gyűjtöttek. A génusz egyetlen ismert faja a síkvidéki esőerdők maradványaiban él. Mind a génuszról, mind a fajról megfelelő diagnózist és leírást adunk, hangsúlyozva az utolsó potrohlemezek tulajdonságainak fontosságát. 32 ábrával.

* Levelező szerző.

Kulcsszavak – Kakamega Erdő, Kalinzu Erdő, Kenya, Kibale Erdő, síkvidéki esőerdő, *Megalonycta*, Uganda

ÁBRAMAGYARÁZAT

1–10. ábrák. A *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. valamint a *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* és *M. inversa* imágói: 1 = *C. politzari*, HT, hím, Kenya, Kakamega, NMK-INV-T-672, gen. prep. MC 3-2022 (coll. NMK); 2 = *C. politzari*, PT, hím, Kenya, Kakamega, gen. prep. KA1431m (coll. ZSM); 3 = *C. politzari*, PT, hím, Kenya, Kakamega, gen. prep. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 4 = *C. politzari*, PT, hím, Uganda, Kibale N. P., gen. prep. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 5 = *C. politzari*, PT, hím, Kenya, Western Kakamega Forest N. R., gen. prep. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 6 = *C. politzari*, PT, nőstény, Kenya, Nyugati Kakamega Erdő N. R., gen. prep. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 7 = *M. forsteri*, hím, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA894m (coll. ZMUC); 8 = *M. forsteri*, nőstény, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA2191f (coll. GB); 9 = *M. paragrapha*, hím, Dél-Afrikai Köztársaság, gen. prep. KA2121m (coll. SMNS); 10 = *M. inversa*, nőstény, Ruanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, gen. prep. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Méretléc = 10 mm. (Fotók – Njoroge L.: 1. ábra; Kiss Á.: 2–10. ábrák)

11–16. ábrák. A *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. valamint a *Megalonycta forsteri* és *M. inversa* hímjének ivarszervei (valvák és aedeagus evertált vesica-val): 11 = *C. politzari*, HT, Kenya, Kakamega, NMK-INV-T-672, gen. prep. MC 3-2022 (coll. NMK) (nem méretarányos, evertálatlan vesica); 12 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, gen. prep. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 13 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, gen. prep. KA1432m (coll. ZSM); 14 = *C. politzari*, PT, Uganda, Kibale N. P., gen. prep. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 15 = *M. forsteri*, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA895m (coll. ZMUC); 16 = *M. inversa*, HT, Tanzánia, gen. prep. KA1471m (coll. MfN). Méretléc = 1 mm. (Fotók – Njoroge L.: 11. ábra; Kiss Á.: 12–16. ábrák). A valva tövi illatszőrök háttére a grafikai lehetőségek korlátai miatt sötétebb.

17–21. ábrák. A *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. valamint a *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* és *M. inversa* nőstényének ivarszervei: 17 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Nyugati Kakamega Erdő N. R., gen. prep. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 18 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Nyugati Kakamega Erdő N. R., gen. prep. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 19 = *M. forsteri*, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA2191f (coll. GB); 20 = *M. paragrapha*, Dél-Afrikai Köztársaság, gen. prep. KA1470f (coll. MfN); 21 = *M. inversa*, Ruanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, gen. prep. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Méretléc = 1 mm. (Fotók: Kiss Á.)

22–27. ábrák. A *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. valamint a *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* és *M. inversa* hímjének 7. és 8. potrohlemezei: 22 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Kakamega, gen. prep. KA979m (coll. ZSM); 23 = *C. politzari*, PT, Uganda, Kibale N. P., gen. prep. KA1870m (coll. MfN); 24 = *M. forsteri*, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA895m (coll. ZMUC); 25 = *M. forsteri*, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA1417m (coll. GB); 26 = *M. paragrapha*, Dél-Afrikai Köztársaság, gen. prep. KA2126m (coll. SMNS); 27 = *M. inversa*, HT, Tanzánia, gen. prep. KA1471m (coll. MfN). Bal oldalasi, jobb oldal háti lemezek. Méretléc = 1 mm. (Fotók: Kiss Á.)

28–32. ábrák. A *Corniculonycta politzari* sp. nov. valamint a *Megalonycta forsteri*, *M. paragrapha* és *M. inversa* nőtényének 7. potrohlemeze: 28 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Nyugati Kakamega Erdő N. R., gen. prep. KA2113f (coll. SMNS); 29 = *C. politzari*, PT, Kenya, Nyugati Kakamega Erdő N. R., gen. prep. KA2114f (coll. SMNS); 30 = *M. forsteri*, Etiópia, gen. prep. KA2191f (coll. GB); 31 = *M. paragrapha*, Dél-Afrikai Köztársaság, gen. prep. KA1470f (coll. MfN); 32 = *M. inversa*, Ruanda, ex. coll. Laporte, MHNG-ENTO-98068, gen. prep. KA2276f (coll. MHNG). Bal oldal háti, jobb oldal hasi lemezek. Méretléc = 1 mm. (Fotók: Kiss Á.)